

THE USE OF FERTILIZER AND HYDROGEN PEROXIDE IN THE BIODEGRADATION OF CRUDE OIL.

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ABSTRACT

Biostimulation is a process by which nutrients and/or oxygen are added to enhance bioremediation. This study involved the use of *Klebsiella sp.* in the biodegradation of crude oil, and comparing two different methods of biostimulation - addition of oxygen (hydrogen peroxide 0.03% v/v) and addition of nutrients (fertilizer: NPK 15-15-15; 30% w/w). The microcosm experiments took place for a period of seven weeks during which the heterotrophic plate count and estimation of oil and grease content were both used to monitor the progress of biodegradation of the crude oil. Heterotrophic counts ranged from 1.0×10^3 to 3.1×10^5 CFU/gram of soil while, the oil and grease content ranged between 120mg/litre and 480 mg/litre. Treatments containing hydrogen peroxide as the only enhancement recorded the highest heterotrophic counts as well as the lowest oil and grease content at the end of the seven week duration; indicating that in this study, oxygenation had a more profound effect on increasing the rate of biodegradation of crude oil as opposed to NPK fertilizer. The heterotrophic count of the samples treated with one or both of the factors was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$); however, on analysis of the oil and grease content of the samples treated with one or both of the factors, it was not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$).

KEYWORDS: bioremediation, hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria, hydrogen peroxide, NPK fertilizer, soil.

INTRODUCTION

Bioremediation involves the use of microorganisms to remove pollutants (Atlas and Pramer, 1990). The two general approaches to bioremediation are environmental modification, such as through fertilizer application and aeration, and addition of adapted microbial hydrocarbon degraders by seeding (Atlas and Bartha, 1992).

Since microorganisms require nitrogen and phosphorus for incorporation into biomass, the availability of these nutrients within the same area as the hydrocarbon is critical, also aerobic conditions are necessary for effective use of microbial oxidation of hydrocarbons to remove oil pollutants from the environment (Atlas and Bartha, 1992).

Nutrient availability, especially of nitrogen and phosphorus seems to be the most limiting factor in the biodegradation of petroleum hydrocarbons. It was confirmed that these nutrients enhance growth of microorganisms, which leads to more rapid decomposition of contaminants (Coulon *et al.*, 2004; Chaineau *et al.*, 2005). And oxygen delivery is an important factor in promoting the proliferation and growth of aerobic microorganisms when biologically degrading chemical contaminants such as petroleum hydrocarbons (Frycek *et al.*, 2004). Addition of nutrients could be in the form of organic (manure, poultry and livestock droppings, *et cetera*) or inorganic (for instance, chemical fertilizers). Addition of oxygen during bioremediation could be achieved by tilling, or through the use of oxygen-release products such as solid peroxygen compounds which are directly derived from hydrogen peroxide or are produced via electrochemical oxidation (Frycek *et al.*, 2004). Such compounds include among others, sodium perborate, sodium percarbonate, and potassium hydroperoxysulphate.

The aim of this study is to compare the addition of oxygen and addition of fertilizer as methods of biostimulation in the biodegradation of crude oil by bacteria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Soil Samples

The soil samples were obtained from,

- (i) Sites contaminated with petroleum in a mechanic workshop.
- (ii) Garden soil with no history of petroleum contamination from Department of Microbiology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

The soil samples were collected using a clean spatula from a depth of not more than 20cm. They were stored in clean polythene bags and kept for future use.

Isolation of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria: Ten grams of soil sample obtained from the mechanic's workshop was suspended in 90ml of sterile distilled water in a conical flask. The suspension was subjected to shaking for five minutes, 1ml of the supernatant was measured with a sterile pipette and added to a 150 ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 50ml sterile nutrient broth and 1 % crude oil (0.5ml), the Erlenmeyer flask was sealed with cotton wool and incubated on a rotary shaker at 300r.p.m for five weeks at room temperature.

At the end of the incubation period, a loop full of the contents of the Erlenmeyer flask was inoculated on nutrient agar, and incubated at 35°C for 24h. The colonies obtained were all sub-cultured on nutrient agar slants respectively, and stored in the refrigerator.

Characterisation of the isolates was achieved using biochemical tests (Cheesebrough, 2001). A 24 hrs culture of each of the isolate was used to determine their gram reaction. The following biochemical tests were carried out: catalase test, methyl-red test, voges-prokauer test, indole test, motility test, triple sugar iron test, urease utilization, and citrate test respectively.

Screening of Bacterial Isolates for Petroleum-hydrocarbon Degradation

The verification of petroleum-hydrocarbon degradation by the isolates obtained was carried out using mineral salts medium (250ml) with the following constitution: K_2HPO_4 (0.5g/l), $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ (100mg/l), $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ (5mg/l), $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ (0.5g/l), $CaCl_2$ (5mg/l), $MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (0.25mg/l), $ZnSO_4$ (0.25mg/l), $CuSO_4$ (0.25mg/l), Cobaltous chloride (0.25mg/l).

The pH of the medium was adjusted to 7.0 using dilute hydrochloric acid solution and was dispensed into six Erlenmeyer flasks and autoclaved at 121°C at 15atm for 15mins. Each isolate (Mcfarland's standard 7 was used to standardise the inoculum size) was added to the sterile medium at 10% (v/w) and crude oil was added at 0.5% (v/v). The flasks were incubated at room temperature on an orbital shaker at 300 r.p.m for five days, absorbance readings (at 540nm) were taken after a 24h period and on the fifth day of incubation respectively. The absorbance change of the mineral media was used as the evaluation criteria for the isolates' adaptation to the medium used and their ability to degrade crude oil (Ilyina *et al.*, 2003).

Klebsiella sp was observed to have the highest growth rate; as such it was used for the subsequent microcosm experiment.

Biodegradation Experiment

Determination of optimum concentrations of NPK fertiliser and hydrogen peroxide for biodegradation.

Two different concentrations of NPK fertiliser and hydrogen peroxide solution respectively, were tested in order to ascertain the ideal one to use subsequently.

Mineral salts medium (36ml) with the same constitution as mentioned above was placed in six Erlenmeyer flasks, and its pH adjusted to 7.0 using sodium hydroxide solution. It was sterilised in an autoclave at 121°C at 15atm for 15mins, and the following setup was carried out:

TABLE 1: Set-Up For Soil Biodegradation

ERLENMEYER (250ml)	FLASK	CONTENT
1		10% v/w <i>Klebsiella sp.</i> + 0.5% v/w H ₂ O ₂ + crude oil (0.5%v/w)
2		10% v/w <i>Klebsiella sp.</i> + 30% w/w NPK + crude oil (0.5%v/w)
3		10% v/w <i>Klebsiella sp.</i> + 15% w/w NPK + crude oil (0.5%v/w)
4		10% v/w <i>Klebsiella sp.</i> + 0.3% v/w H ₂ O ₂ + crude oil (0.5%v/w)
5		Mineral media only
6		10% v/w <i>Klebsiella sp.</i> + crude oil (0.5%v/w)

The Erlenmeyer flasks were then incubated on an orbital shaker at 300r.p.m at room temperature for seven days. The absorbance readings at 540nm using *Cecil Ce 1020* spectrophotometer were taken on the days 1 and 7 respectively.

The concentrations of NPK fertilizer and hydrogen peroxide that gave the highest absorbance readings were used for the microcosm experiments.

Soil microcosm experiments

A garden soil sample with no apparent petroleum contamination was air dried for two weeks and then crushed and sieved. Twenty five kilograms of the sample was weighed into five polythene bags autoclaved, and transferred into five clean plastic bowls. Holes were bored into the base of the bowls to allow aeration. The suspension of *Klebsiella sp.* used corresponded to Mcfarland's standard 7 and it was measured to a concentration of 1% (v/w). The concentration of NPK fertilizer used was 30% w/w while, 0.3% v/w was used for the hydrogen peroxide. The following treatment system was carried out:

Table 2: Set-Up For Soil Microcosm Studies

Treatment system	Contents
T1	Crude oil + <i>Klebsiella sp.</i>
T2	Crude oil + <i>Klebsiella sp.</i> + NPK
T3	Crude oil + <i>Klebsiella sp.</i> + H ₂ O ₂
T4	Crude oil + <i>Klebsiella sp.</i> + NPK + H ₂ O ₂
T5	Crude oil only

The treatment systems were incubated at room temperature for seven weeks; the water holding capacity was adjusted to 50% using sterile distilled water.

Heterotrophic bacterial counts were carried out on a weekly basis using pour plate method. Oil and grease content, was determined on a fortnight basis.

Heterotrophic bacterial count:

One gram of soil sample from each of the treatment systems was measured aseptically using a chemical balance and suspended in 9ml of sterile distilled water, then a ten-fold dilution was carried out up to dilution 10⁻³. 1ml of dilutions 10⁻² and 10⁻³ were aseptically inoculated on nutrient agar plates using the pour plate method and incubated at 35°C for 24h, the colonies obtained were counted.

Determination of Oil and grease content:

Gravimetric analysis was used to monitor the hydrocarbon content of the soil samples over the seven week period. Petroleum ether was used to extract the oil content present in the soil samples (Standard Methods, 1985).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three genera of Gram-negative rods were obtained (*Alcaligenes*, *Klebsiella* and *Acinetobacter*), two genera of Gram-positive rods which include, *Xanthomonas* and *Bacillus* and one genus of Gram-positive cocci, *Staphylococcus*.

The hydrocarbon utilisation by each isolate was determined by taking their absorbance readings (optical density) on days 1 and 5 respectively. Emulsification of the crude oil was noticed in all the test vessels containing the isolates, but to varying degrees. Increase in optical density was related with the microbial growth, which also shows the extent of degradation of the petroleum hydrocarbon. *Klebsiella sp.* had the highest percentage of emulsification (40%) while, *Acinetobacter sp.* had the lowest percentage (-0.8%). The other isolates had the following percentages, *Bacillus sp.* (20%), *Alcaligenes sp.* (24%), *Xanthomonas sp.* (9.6%) and *Staphylococcus sp.* (8%).

During the first week of the microcosm experiments (Table 3), a low heterotrophic count was recorded for all the treatment sets probably because, the bacteria was in the lag phase of growth. However, the subsequent weeks exhibited an improvement in the bacterial growth before eventually a decline occurred. This decline in growth could be attributed to a depletion of carbon source for energy and growth requirements. The same trend was also observed by Chorom *et al.*, (2010). The control treatment (T5) showed no bacterial growth all through the period of biodegradation, this treatment was devoid of *Klebsiella sp.* and both factors (NPK fertiliser and hydrogen peroxide), it only contained crude oil.

The hydrocarbon utilising bacteria (HUB) represented as the heterotrophic count (Table 3) was observed to increase during the microcosm experiments and then drop after the seven week period, perhaps as a result of depletion of the carbon source (crude oil) as well as inorganic nutrients. The subsequent low HUB count could also be as result of the oil-resistant components with high chain and within less remaining nutrients (Schaefer and Juliane, 2007).

The treatment sets containing NPK fertiliser had the lowest HBC (Heterotrophic bacterial count) at the end of the seven week bioremediation period, this could be as a result of the high concentration of ammonia gas released from the fertiliser, because most commercial fertilisers supply nitrogen in soluble forms, such as nitrate or ammonium (Ayotamuno *et al.*, 2003). The highest growth rate (Table 1) was observed between the fourth and sixth week of the microcosm experiment for almost all the soil treatments (T1: 3.1×10^5 CFU/g in the fifth week; T2: 1.1×10^5 cfu/g in the sixth week; T3: 2.4×10^5 CFU/g in the fifth week; T4: 9.1×10^4 CFU/g in the fourth week). A study by Chorom *et al.*, (2010) reported the highest growth of HUB in the fifth week as well.

TABLE 3 HETEROTROPHIC BACTERIAL COUNT OF SOIL SAMPLES.

Treatment	Counts Log(cfu/g)						
	wk 1	wk 2	wk 3	wk 4	wk 5	wk 6	wk 7
T1	1.0×10^3	7.6×10^4	7.9×10^4	1.6×10^5	3.1×10^5	1.7×10^5	8.8×10^4
T2	2.0×10^3	4.0×10^3	7.0×10^3	2.8×10^4	6.6×10^4	1.1×10^5	2.0×10^3
T3	4.0×10^3	1.4×10^5	2.2×10^5	2.3×10^5	2.4×10^5	1.2×10^5	1.9×10^5
T4	2.0×10^3	3.0×10^3	1.7×10^4	9.1×10^4	1.4×10^4	1.6×10^4	3.0×10^3
T5	N.G	N.G	N.G	N.G	N.G	N.G	N.G

T1 – T5: Garden soil

T1: contains only *Klebsiella sp.* and crude oil

T2: contains *Klebsiella sp.*, NPK fertiliser and crude oil

T3: contains *Klebsiella sp.*, hydrogen peroxide and crude oil

T4: contains *Klebsiella sp.*, hydrogen peroxide, NPK fertiliser and crude oil

T5: control (contains only crude oil)

N.G: No visible growth

Comparism between the treatments with one or both of the enhancements (hydrogen peroxide and NPK fertilizer) showed that their heterotrophic counts were statistically significant (Fig. 1). However the treatments containing hydrogen peroxide as the only enhancement had the highest bacterial count. This shows that oxygenation enhanced the breakdown of the petroleum hydrocarbons better than addition of nutrients thus the high heterotrophic counts obtained. There was a significant difference between the means of these treatments ($P < 0.05$). However, the role of nutrient addition cannot be overlooked, In addition to a nitrogen deficiency in oil-soaked soil, certain nutrients like phosphorus may be growth-rate limiting (Jobson *et al.*, 1974). Some other

researches have also shown increase in biodegradation of petroleum with adding of fertilizer and ventilation (Ramsay and Partners, 2000; Chorom *et al.*, 2010). Another important factor that might have contributed to the strong impact of oxygenation is the nature of the soil sample used in the bioremediation experiments. It is of the sandy loam texture which has sufficient air space to allow for maximum oxygen availability to the bacteria. It is for this same reason that soil oxygen diffusion is very low in water-logged soil and thus, not keeping up with the demands of heterotrophic decomposition processes (Atlas and Bartha, 1992).

Treatments are statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

The oil and grease content (Table 4) was evaluated to monitor the progress of the petroleum hydrocarbons during the experiment, and it was found to decrease during the period of biodegradation. The treatments containing hydrogen peroxide either as a single enhancement (T3:120mg/litre) or in combination with NPK fertiliser (T4:140mg/litre) had the lowest oil and grease content at the end of the seven weeks, thus indicating that hydrogen peroxide played a more vital role in the utilization of crude oil in this experiment.

A steady decline was noticed in the oil and grease content in all the treatments however, the treatments containing *Klebsiella sp.* and at least one of the factors under study (T2, T3, T4) showed higher hydrocarbon losses than the treatments containing only *Klebsiella sp.* (T1), as shown in table 4. This could be attributed to the fact that the bacteria require one or both of the factors (biostimulation) in order to degrade the crude oil efficiently (Atlas and Bartha, 1992). Thus emphasizing the role of biostimulation in the bioremediation of crude oil.

The control treatment had the highest value of oil and grease content after the seven week period; this could be due to the fact that the hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria, *Klebsiella sp.* was not present in that treatment. However, one way analysis of variance revealed that there was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) in all the treatments. This might be an indication that the biodegradation of the crude oil was more evident in the heterotrophic bacterial count as opposed to the measurement of oil and grease content (Fig 2)

Table 4 Oil And Grease Content (mg/litre) Of The Samples During Microcosm Studies

Treatment	wk 1	wk 3	wk 5	wk 7
T1	470	430	340	300
T2	420	390	260	240
T3	340	220	150	120
T4	500	400	350	210
T5	400	350	250	230

No significant difference for all treatment sets. ($P > 0.05$)

No significant difference for all treatment sets. ($P > 0.05$)

CONCLUSION

Biostimulation (either in the form of nutrient addition and/or addition of oxygen) plays an essential role in the biodegradation of crude oil by bacteria. In this study, both NPK fertilizer application and addition of hydrogen peroxide both had an impact on the enhancement of biodegradation of crude oil however, the latter was observed to have a more significant impact on the heterotrophic count of the bacteria used in the experiment. The use of fertilizer and hydrogen peroxide are both viable means of increasing rates of biodegradation of petroleum products but they should be used in concentrations that would not constitute additional problems for the environment where they are being applied.

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